

CONSUMER ATTITUDE TOWARDS CLOTHING APPAREL OF UNIQUE DESIGNER BRANDS IN BANGLADESH

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Abstract

Early consumer behavior researchers rarely focused on the attitudinal dimension of clothing buyers although it has always remained as a prime building block of the Consumer Behavior (CB). This study adopts multiple regression techniques to analyze the data collected from 140 apparel buyers to examine the determinants of consumer attitude with respect to unique designer clothing brands of Bangladesh. The analysis reveals that out of seven identified predictors, three items, namely- celebrity endorsement, quality, and aesthetic aspects, significantly influence consumer attitude towards unique designer clothing apparel brands. The findings from this study is of critical importance because it contributes to clothing marketers' knowledge about the prominence of Consumer Behavior (CB) in the fashion marketing paradigm and offers an extensive understanding of the drivers of consumer attitude with respect to the unique designer clothing apparel brands.

Keywords : *Consumer attitude, Clothing apparel, Unique designer brand, Bangladesh.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Bangladesh is coming out as one of the next-doors for the engine of business growth with the conceptualization of the nation's burgeoning consumer class. As per the Boston Consulting Group report published in 2015, the current 7% Middle and Affluent Consumers (MAC) having an annual household income of \$5,000, is estimated to be tripled by 2025, to about 34 million. This evidence suggests a potential purchasing power of middle-class people for branded consumer products. In this regard, the nation's significant garments manufacturing sector is occupying the second position for sizable exporting after China (Islam et al., 2014). The yearly records of Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, 2018 identified strong preferences among the mass of Bangladeshi towards designer clothing brands with the monthly per capita income of BDT 2,553. Thus, numerous fashion houses are considering this gigantic clothing market and their attitude formation pattern in establishing their brand identity (Rahman and Mannan, 2018). The Fashion Entrepreneurs Association of Bangladesh (FEAB) has counted around 5,500 fashion houses operating with an annual turnover of Tk. 80-85 billion approximately. These brands are playing a laudable role in meeting local consumers' unique demand by an effort of clothing business expansion (Taplin, 2014; Turker and Altuntas, 2014).

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Although some researchers have paid attention to consumers' purchase behavior and its associated factors with regard to clothing brands, (Kumar et al., 2009; Lee et al., 2008; Chowdhury and Akter, 2018) little is known about what influences their buying attitude towards those brands. Purchase behavior is the outcome of positive attitude formation and evaluation towards a particular product (Ajzen, 1985; Dickson and Littrell, 1996). Marketers are always interested to know ultimate consumer behavior regarding brands as behavior often involves particular action- purchasing. Thus, the literature on purchase behavior formation is rich. But this literature does not capture in-depth comprehension of purchase attitude development which has been identified as the building block of ultimate consumer behavior (Ajzen, 1985).

In this recent business environment, marketers are formulating solid marketing strategies with a keen understanding of the behavioral intention, feelings, and beliefs of consumers towards a specific brand. This behavioral perspective of consumers consists of a dynamic element namely "attitude" that acts as a motivation for action (Ajzen, 2020). The difference between attitude and behavior signifies that attitude involves internal evaluation about the product, people, and other objects while behavior relates to physical action toward that object. Thus, while a consumer views a product advertisement, information is likely to enter into his black box and later converted into an internal product judgment. Based on this judgment, the consumer decides whether to purchase the product or not (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1970).

Recent emerging trends in the fashion industry such as globalization, availability of vast choices, higher customer service expectation, creation of personal identity, particularly public figures endorsement, etc. are presenting unprecedented competitions for designer clothing brands (Hogg and Michell, 1996; Chowdhury and Akter, 2018). Because of such heightened competition, brands are increasingly focusing on understanding behavioral and purchase intention aspects of consumers (Ahmed and Ahmed, 2013; Chowdhury and Akter, 2018). However, there is a lack of strategic focus on "attitude" formation which has been identified as a prime driver of intention and behavior (Ajzen, 1985; Dickson and Littrell, 1996). In case of adopting the "attitude" measurement, some challenges that a marketer faces include how a consumer obtains product-related verbal information from translating emotional and visual elements of advertising (Lutz, 1985; Mitchell and Olson, 1981; Cacioppo et al., 1986).

Past researches on fashionable designer clothing brands have concentrated on a variety of issues such as fashion attributes influencing buying behavior (Chowdhury and Akter, 2018); service quality, satisfaction, and loyalty analysis (Islam et al., 2012); purchase behavior toward local vs. foreign brand (Kumar et al., 2009); online purchase behavior (Rahman and Mannan, 2018); purchase intention (Lee et al., 2008); clothing benefits sought (Park and Sullivan, 2009); consumer decision-making style (Wang et al., 2004), clothing brand loyalty (Oh and Fiorito, 2002), etc. Though "attitude" is often termed as a forecaster of behavior in psychology studies, the existing clothing literature is almost in dark about discussing the attitudinal

perspective of consumers. Therefore, the broad objective of the study is to investigate how the attitude is developed among Bangladeshi consumers in the designer clothing brand context. Notably, this study has two specific objectives:

- To analyze the association between consumer attitude and the identified factors: celebrity endorsement, quality, word-of-mouth, aesthetic, customer service, personal identity, and country-of-origin
- To empirically validate the influence of the identified factors on developing consumer attitudes in a designer clothing brand context

Theoretically, the present study aims to provide a better understanding of the way a consumer develops positive or negative brand attitude through an internal product or service evaluation. By examining the impact of influential factors on building consumer attitude in the fashion industry, more precisely in the designer clothing apparel context, the findings offer practical implications for the brand managers interested in developing solid marketing strategies through the proper blending of these identified factors.

This research comprises five parts. In the beginning, it reviews the relevant previous studies related to consumer attitude, clothing apparel, and determinants of consumer attitudes and hypotheses are formulated accordingly. Next, a conceptual framework is presented for the study. After that, research methodology and data analytical tools and techniques are discussed. Then, the discussion and summarization of the findings are provided. The final section ends with a discussion specifying theoretical and managerial implications while mentioning present limitations and future research direction.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Marketing Research on Designer Clothing Brands

Designer clothing as a trendy product category represents an interesting area of academic research for fashion marketing scholars (Bakewell et al., 2006; O’Cass, 2004; Auty and Elliott, 1998). The prior researches exploring designer clothing brands represent diverse series of research. The fashion marketing literature recognizes designer clothing brands as a part of diversified industry and these are highly researched in consumer involvement and behavior-oriented research (O’Cass and Choy, 2008; O’Cass, 2004; Khare and Rakesh, 2010; Rahman and Mannan, 2018; Rahman et al., 2020). Former research has also centered on purchase intention of apparel brand (Lee et al., 2008); online purchase behavior (Rahman and Mannan, 2018); clothing benefits sought (Park and Sullivan, 2009); Status and clothing brand consciousness (O’Cass and Siahtiri, 2013) and alike. Although these are enormous and diverse, existing researches rarely provide any glimpse into the consumer attitude formation towards designer clothing apparel brands (Table 1). Therefore, it is significant to investigate the attitudinal perspective of consumers and how it is influenced through various attributes.

The contemporary researches describe the fashion industry as comprehensive and extensive due to its constant involvement in broadening of consumer's understanding related with consumer's lifestyle, cultural dimensions, and fashion trend. As the present marketplace is loaded with a huge variety of clothing brands, such understanding of consumers is required to know their buying decision and relationship-making process with brands (Rahman and Mannan, 2018). In forming the relationship, consumers retrieve various brand-related emotional and visual cues from advertisements and later transform them into product-related specific information. Such information conversion will lead consumers to develop positive or negative brand-related attitudes (Lutz, 1985; Mitchell and Olson, 1981; Cacioppo et al., 1986). Therefore, having knowledge about consumers' desire and their attitudes towards designer clothing brands represent an authentic and pertinent study topic both in the fashion industry and Consumer Behavior (CB) discipline. Consumers use several dimensions such as personal learning, experiences, family, friends, and marketing strategy in creating a positive or negative attitude towards a clothing brand (Eagly and Chaiken, 1993). Since attitude is the building block of consumer behavior (Ajzen, 2020), a good understanding of what constitutes consumer attitude and its implications in selecting clothing brands is necessary.

2.2 Consumer Attitude

In the Consumer Behavior (CB) discipline, one of the greatest challenges involves not just evaluating attitude towards an object but to assess it towards performing a specific behavior (Fishbein, 1967). Different scholars attempt to define the term "attitude" from different dimensions. The old-fashioned perspective defined attitude as the totality of behavior that leads to or points toward some particular activity of the organism. Contemporary research tries to explain attitude as the dynamic element of behavior that acts as a prime motivator for any action (Ajzen, 2020). The author further enhanced the definition as the learned predisposition of human beings upon which an individual would make a response to an object or an idea. However, within the context of marketing, the simple definition of consumer attitude ranges from the composition of a consumer's beliefs, feelings to the development of purchase intention towards any offering. A more complex perspective of consumer attitude defines it as the function of behavioral belief where a certain outcome or experience is the result of the probability of conducting a behavior of interest (Ajzen, 2020). Thus, the summation or combination of this behavioral belief can lead a consumer to generate a particular product or service-related attitude. When consumers build a positive or negative attitude towards a particular offering, they try to create an evaluative association between that offering and its characteristics (Kim and Karpova, 2010). Such evaluations, made over time, can affect their buying and shopping habits. Thus, it can be concluded that consumers' purchase intention and behavior are the result of having a strong, positive product or service-related attitude (Ajzen, 1980; Dickson and Littrell, 1996; Triandis, 1977).

2.3 Determinants of Consumer Attitude towards Clothing Apparel Brand

2.3.1 Relationship between Celebrity Endorsement and Consumer Attitude

A celebrity endorsement is an approach for gaining and keeping the attention of consumers as the celebrity tries to build up a connection between the brand and consumer. Some authors mentioned the positive sides of using celebrities for designer clothing brands. The advantages range from drawing attention to building a polished image and introducing a brand extension to repositioning a brand (Erdogan, 1999). Further researches have been extended towards showing how a particular celebrity can lead a consumer in accumulating experiences that assist them in recalling and creating an intention to buy a particular brand (Jansson and Power, 2010). According to (Atkin and Block, 1983) and (Petty et al., 1983), a celebrity can produce a strong positive attitude toward product advertising, thus generating greater purchase intention among consumers. The appropriateness of using a celebrity is analyzed with regard to the “purchase-risk” dimension in the study of (Friedman and Friedman, 1979) and (Atkin and Block, 1983). The findings reveal that celebrity endorsement is required when a consumer’s purchase decision involves high social and psychological risk. Moreover, it is an effective selling strategy for products and services involved with status and symbols as celebrities are the people holding high status in society. The conclusion is that appropriate celebrity usage can significantly influence consumer attitude toward designer clothing brands since these brands have status and symbol-attached offerings for consumers. Based on this observation, it can be drawn that:

H1: Celebrity Endorsement has a significant influence on consumer attitude development.

2.3.2 Relationship between Quality and Consumer Attitude

A number of earlier studies on clothing apparel represent that brand quality and buying attitude of consumers are interconnected with each other. The studies provide indications that reliability, durability of garments, and perceived quality are appropriate items for measuring quality of clothing apparel brands. However, some researchers added more components in the evaluation of quality aspect of clothing apparel brands. For example, (Chowdhury and Akter, 2018) added price attributes along with style and design while (Hourigan and Bougoure, 2012) included comfort components as Australian consumers consider it a necessary attribute in selecting clothing apparel. Both studies have come to the point that designer clothing brands and quality perspectives should be considered as intertwined. Apart from quality, designer clothing brands have top-of-mind cues such as brand names, intelligence, luxury, expensiveness, durability, and so on. It is therefore proposed that:

H2: Quality has a significant influence on consumer attitude development.

2.3.3 Relationship between Word-of-mouth and Consumer Attitude

By definition, attitude is a learned tendency that is largely influenced by family and friend's words (Eagly and Chaiken, 1993). This signifies the importance of a personal form of communication about the brand, product, and service. Thus, when a person makes remark to another person about a product or service-related consumption experience, this lends powerful influence over forming positive or negative attitudes (Martin and Frank, 2008). In an attempt to establish a relationship between word-of-mouth and clothing purchase behavior, myriad studies have been undertaken with regard to the fashion industry (Kiecker and Cowles, 2002; McKinney et al., 2004). In the context of the United States, McKinney et al., (2004) explored a direct relationship that exists between clothing item selection and getting positive words from a person's reference group, therefore making this antecedent as one of the prime contributors in consumer attitude formation. So, this can be inferred from earlier studies that the attitude of a consumer towards a designer clothing brand can be significantly related to getting any opinion or remarks from a reference group.

H3: Word-of-mouth has a significant influence on consumer attitude development.

2.3.4 Relationship between Aesthetic Aspect and Consumer Attitude

The fashion clothing brands are considered as prestigious brands by consumers since they encompass different types of social and psychological value perspectives. These are, namely, perceived unique value, perceived conspicuous value, perceived hedonic value, perceived social value, perceived quality value, perceived emotional value and so on. The way a consumer develops his social and psychological values affect his or her perceptions and preferences toward the fashionable designer brand (Prendergast and Wong, 2003). Moreover, the two authors concluded that the reason to choose designer clothing brands can also be attributed to the aesthetic, emotional feeling that a consumer can get through wearing. The fashion clothing literature develops a complex comparison between "hedonistic" and "functional" attributes that consumers undertake to make a trade-off when buying apparel. Such comparison is seen in the study of Parker and Wang (2016) where the authors include fashionable design, style under hedonistic perspective while durability, perceived quality, reliability are under functional attributes. Therefore, it is proposed that:

H4: Aesthetic aspect has a significant influence on consumer attitude development.

2.3.5 Relationship between Customer Service and Consumer Attitude

Quite a lot of earlier studies have come to the point that customer service is the crucial element in creating and maintaining a favorable attitude of consumers. Such a favorable attitude will drive consumers to undertake behavioral actions such as purchasing or spreading good words (Kyj, 1984; Porter, 1997). The previous two authors further identified customer service tools as a way to differentiate the brand

when the degree of rivalry in the industry is extreme. This implies that as a saturated industry with lots of designer clothing brands, the tool “customer service” will be a differentiating factor for shaping favorable attitudes among consumers. Furthermore, the study of Moye (2000) reveals that consumers select brands based on the availability of higher customer services. These services can take a variety of forms such as convenience store location, knowledgeable sales staff, smooth payment facilities, gift certificate, gift wrapping and so on. The study further classified these services under two categories namely convenience and auxiliary service. Thus, it is hypothesized that:

H5: Customer service has a significant influence on consumer attitude development

2.3.6 Relationship between Personal Identity and Consumer Attitude

Consumer Behavior (CB) researchers have placed a substantial amount of attention on the personality aspect as it is asserted to be a significant effect on attitude development. As a whole, brand marketers of fashionable items are highly eager to uncover the way that the personality of a person characterizes consumption (O’Cass, 2004). In this vein, the personality of a person can be best understood by observing his particular lifestyle and belonging to a specific social group (Murphy, 1992). This lifestyle pattern can take the form of simple utilitarian one to aesthetic or hedonic form, the highest level of consumption pattern. An explicit link between personality exhibition and clothing apparel brand is established in the study of Kamineni and O’Cass, (2000). As per the study, the expression of personality can largely happen publicly through using apparel as it possesses public meaning and satisfies the needs of identity and image building. This implies that a strong personality-oriented consumer often selects clothing as a way of managing impression in society. Since hedonic consumption-oriented consumers are more involved in using designer clothing brands, it can be inferred that the attitude of consumers toward brands can be significantly impacted by their degree of personality. In this regard, the following hypothesis could be drawn for the study:

H6: Personal identity has a significant influence on consumer attitude development.

2.3.7 Relationship between Country-of-origin and Consumer Attitude

An increasing research interest seen among the researchers is to make a comparative analysis of foreign and local clothing brands. The reason is to explore why the consumers from emerging economies are attracted to brands of developed countries (Kumar et al., 2009). In this regard, lots of prior studies have adopted the “country-of-origin” variable as it is frequently extracted for evaluating the quality of products (Hong and Wyer Jr, 1990; Li and Wyer Jr, 1994; Maheswaran, 1994; Gürhan-Canli and Maheswaran, 2000). Consumers take a “made-in” cue to justify whether clothing brands are qualified to have the title “superiority” or not. The failure in achieving this title led consumers to focus on the particular country’s competency to understand

why the brand is inferior in quality (Lin and Chen, 2006). Thus, the source of production perspective is undertaken in several studies as an evaluative criterion for measuring clothing brand's success (Dutton, 2006; Park et al., 2009; Jegethesan et al., 2012; Prasad, 2012). Each and every study mentioned here support the following hypothesis that:

H7: Country-of-origin has a significant influence on consumer attitude development.

In the following section, some of the contemporary studies (from 2012 to 2020) on designer clothing brands are summarized:

Table 1 : Adopted with modification from (Rahman et al., 2020)

Author (s)	Background of research	List of variables		Outcomes of the research
		Predictor(s)	Dependent variable(s)	
(Goldsmith et al., 2012)	How clothing behavior of consumers gets influenced by materialism, brand engagement level, and status consumption nature?	Materialism, brand engagement, status consumption	Consumer involvement, brand loyalty	All the predictors have positively related with involvement and brand loyalty.
(O'Cass and Siahtiri, 2014)	Measuring young adults' consumption behavior through considering clothing status and brand status perspective.	Status consumption behavior	Perception of brand status and preference for brand	Adult's status consciousness has a considerable impact on forming perception about brand status and preference for the brand.

(Su, 2016)	Analyzing brand equity development from the perspective of fast fashion	Brand awareness	Perceived value and brand personality	A consumer's brand awareness level positively influences in building perceived value and brand personality.
(Chang and Fan, 2017)	Factors affecting the continuous relationship between consumer and brand in the social network environment.	Engagement, Social interaction tie, utilitarian – hedonic value, self-image congruence and affective brand commitment	Continuous intention to use	Continuous intention to use is positively influenced by engagement and affective brand commitment.
(Rahman and Mannan, 2018)	Purchase behavior of domestic clothing brands.	Information adoption and brand experience	Purchase behavior	A consumer's online buying behavior is positively associated with information adoption and brand experience.
(Lee et al., 2018)	Analyzing the attitude and purchase intention of young consumers in the context of cultural differences.	Perceived conspicuousness value, perceived uniqueness value, perceived social value, perceived hedonic value, perceived quality value, brand familiarity	Consumer's attitude and purchase intention	The association between a consumer's luxury brand response and cultural differences is moderated by perceived conspicuous, social, and quality values.

(Su et al., 2019)	Millennials' perceptions and consumption behavior towards sustainable designer clothing.	Personal value and sustainability knowledge	Consumer attitude	A consumer's attitude towards sustainable apparel is positively influenced by his value and knowledge about sustainability.
(Jain, 2020)	Understanding purchase intention of luxury brands by considering subjective norms of Generation Y consumer.	Consumer attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control	Luxury purchase intention	The purchase intention of luxury brands is positively impacted by the subjective norms of the consumer.
(Jain and Mishra, 2020)	Analyzing consumption behavior of luxury fashion brands in sharing economy.	Fashion involvement, Economic benefits, social projection, self-pleasing experience, past sustainable behavior and perceived risk	Intention to consume luxury fashion brand	The consumption intention of fashionable luxury brands is highly influenced by social projection items.

3. THE CONCEPTUAL MODEL FOR THE STUDY

Figure 1 : A proposed conceptual model for the Study

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study population consists of upper and upper-middle class; status-conscious; fashion-oriented clothing buyers from Bangladesh. This population segment has been selected because of their high involvement with prestige, class consciousness, value orientation that goes with preferring branded products (Jones, 1975). The study sample has been drawn from two cities of Bangladesh- Dhaka and Chittagong who belong to the age group of 20-50 years. Here, a non-probability quota sampling procedure has been adopted for generating an appropriate number of respondents. Although this sampling technique lacks assurance of sample representativeness (Malhotra and Dash, 2016), this study attempts to select elements appropriately for a better fit with control characteristics. The data collection activity has been carried out over 12 weeks from November 2020 to January 2021. A total of 203 respondents filled up the questionnaire that yields 144 completed answers resulting in a 70.14 percent response rate. The 59 responses were excluded further from the study due to the incomplete and no information. From each quota, 35 respondents have been selected, resulting in a total of 140 respondents for the study.

An online self-administered survey process has been applied as a part of the data collection procedure. The questionnaire begins with demographic-related questions including gender, age, income, marital status, education, and occupation. Next, some general questions regarding clothing brand purchase behavior are included to orient the respondents about the research context. Finally, the seven measurement

constructs conclude the questionnaire to explore the possible factors affecting consumer attitude. A five-point Likert scale has been appointed with 5 being strongly disagreed and 1 is strongly agreed for measuring each of the construct items. A pre-testing of the questionnaire has been done with 12 clothing buyers whose responses were incorporated for the final revision of the observed variables.

The study applies the Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method for analyzing the proposed research framework as the framework attempts to establish a relationship between the identified factors and consumer attitude. The Statistical data are analyzed by employing SPSS version 23. The data analysis starts with descriptive statistics followed by a reliability test to check the item-construct consistency (Nunnally, 1994) and Pearson correlation analysis. The Multiple Regression Analysis method concludes the analysis by executing the test of hypothesis for the study.

5. FINDINGS & ANALYSES

5.1 Descriptive Analysis

The first section of analysis starts with an examination of demographic sample profile of the study. In the Table 2, information on 140 clothing buyers are analyzed with a list of variables including gender, age, marital status, education, occupation and income level in a percentage form.

Table 2 : Sample Profile

Gender (%)	Age (%)	Marital Status (%)	Education level (%)	Occupation (%)	Monthly family income (%)
Male (39.86)	Below 20 (25)	Single (63.57)	High school/ College (7.86)	Govt. official (2.86)	21,000-40,000 (8.57)
Female (60.14)	21-30 (25)	Married (36.43)	Undergraduate (19)	Professional (34.29)	41,000-60,000 (11.43)
	31-40 (25)		Graduate (40)	Student (25.71)	61,000-80,000 (42.14)
	41-50 (25)		Post-graduate and above (38.57)	Unemployed (5.71)	Above 80,000 (37.89)

Among 140 clothing buyers, participation rate of female is approximately doubled compared with male, indicating female buyers' concentration in the survey. The 20-50 age segments of respondents are distributed in four groups with an interval of 10 and an equal number of 35 participants are selected from each of the group. As quota sampling procedure is adopted for the study, it results in 25 percent respondents' distribution in each age group equally. The respondents are mostly single in their marital status and have a good educational background. The selection of such educated respondent group is justified for the study as the survey has been conducted in online environment through self-administered questionnaire. Additionally, around one-third respondents belong to the professional class with a monthly family income of eighty thousands. Such professional and financial background of respondents justifies their inclusion in upper and upper-middle social segments that prefer to experience different branded products and services.

5.2 Reliability Test

For all the eight constructs including twenty-seven observed variables, the reliability test is conducted. All the items' reliability alpha α values range from 0.847 to 0.860, thus the reliability and validity of the measured variables have been ensured (Nunnally, 1994).

Table 3 : Mean, SD and Cronbach's alpha

Construct	Mean Score	SD Score	Cronbach's Alpha
Aesthetic Aspect			
Fashionable Design	4.03	.93	.852
Style	3.88	1.01	.851
Comfort	4.58	.71	.856
Comfort and Style together	4.45	.73	.856
Personal Identity			
Matching clothing color with skin	3.85	1.18	.859
Personality through unique cloth	3.80	1.11	.854
Social Status	4.25	.95	.856
Consideration of own personality	4.23	.84	.856
Quality			
Reliability	3.79	.98	.849
Durability	3.75	.98	.851
Perceived quality	3.73	1.09	.850
price and quality relationship	4.43	.80	.860
Country-of-origin			
Manufacturing country	3.21	1.09	.853
Local vs. foreign brand	3.74	.98	.860
Celebrity Endorsement			
Usage of favorite celebrity	2.84	1.33	.852
Personality of celebrity	2.95	1.32	.851
Promotion through celebrity	2.90	1.32	.852
Unusual styled depicted through celebrity	3.21	1.23	.857
Customer-service			
Knowledgeable sales staff	3.92	.86	.852
Smooth payment facilities	4.24	.93	.857
Assistance during shopping	4.40	.73	.856

Word-of-mouth			
Delivering on promise	4.35	.78	.853
Family and friends' opinion	4.02	.97	.855
Spreading good words	4.38	.70	.855
Consumer Attitude			
Preference to buy designer brand	3.73	1.0	.847
Pleasurable shopping experience	3.71	.86	.851
Recommendation to other	4.33	.72	.856

5.3 Relationship between Consumer Attitude and Determinants of Consumer Attitude

The relationships between celebrity endorsement and consumer attitude (.489); Quality and consumer attitude (.535); Word-of-mouth and consumer attitude (.361); Aesthetic and consumer attitude (.350); customer service and consumer attitude (.438); personal identity and consumer attitude (2.60); country-of-origin and consumer attitude (.295) indicate that all the constructs except personal identity and country-of-origin have significant bilateral relationship (Gupta, 2001).

Table 4 : Correlation between consumer attitude and the determinants of consumer attitude

	Consumer Attitude	Celebrity Endorsement	Quality	WOM	Aesthetic	Customer Service	Personal Identity	Country-of-origin
Consumer attitude	1							
Celebrity Endorsement	.489*	1						
Quality	.535*	.292	1					
WOM	.361*	.186	.409*	1				
Aesthetic	.350*	.250	.390*	.282	1			
Customer Service	.438*	.156	.336*	.474*	.227	1		
Personal Identity	.260*	.194	.316*	.315*	.327*	.195	1	
Country-of-origin	.295*	.279	.349*	.389*	.194	.258	.269	1

*At 1% (0.01 level), correlation is significant (one-tailed test)

5.4 Inter-relationship among the determinants of consumer attitude

Inter-relationship among determinants of consumer attitude reveals that high and notable association exists between customer service and word-of-mouth (.474) followed by word-of-mouth and quality (.409); aesthetic and quality (.390); country-of-origin and word-of-mouth (.389); country-of-origin and quality (.349); customer

service and quality (.336); personal identity and aesthetic (.327) and personal identity and word-of-mouth (.315) (Table 4). The subsequent investigation of mutual inter-relationship between variables, the influence of independent variables (i.e., celebrity endorsement, personal identity, word-of-mouth, customer service, country-of-origin, aesthetic, and quality) on the dependent variable (i.e. consumer attitude) has been investigated with the analytical method of multiple regression analysis.

5.5 Multiple Regression Analysis

This study attempts to propose a multiple-liner regression model by considering seven predictors and one dependent variable-consumer attitude. In Table 5, it is presented that the coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.478, meaning that 47.8 percent differences in the dependent variable “consumer attitude” can be interpreted by the seven independent variables (determinants of consumer attitude). The suggested research model was appropriate enough for an explanation as the F-value (17.512) is significant at the 0.05 or (p<0.05) level. It specifies the nature of the suggested model as comprehensive and reasonably fit for explaining the relationship between the seven predictors and consumer attitude.

Table 5 : Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.691 ^a	.478	.450	1.30512	.478	17.512	7	134	.000

Source: SPSS output

5.5.1 Statistical Significance of Regression Equation- ANOVA

Table 6 : ANOVA

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	208.803	7	29.829	17.512	.000*
	Residual	228.246	134	1.703		
	Total	437.049	141			
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer attitude toward clothing apparel of unique designer brands						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Celebrity endorsement, Quality, Word-of-mouth, Aesthetic, personal identity, customer service & Country-of-origin						

Source: SPSS output

a. Predictors: (Constant), Celebrity endorsement, Quality, Word-of-mouth, Aesthetic, personal identity, customer service & Country-of-origin.

Now, for the overall test, the null hypothesis is examined through conducting F test. So, the null hypothesis is

$$H_0: \text{Coefficient of multiple determination, } R^2 = 0$$

$$H_1: \text{Coefficient of multiple determination, } R^2 \neq 0$$

Here, $R^2 = .478$ which implies that the null hypothesis is rejected.

This is parallel to examine the null hypothesis in the following way:

$$H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = \beta_5 = \beta_6 = \beta_7 = 0$$

$$H_1 = \text{Not all } \beta\text{s are 0}$$

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in Table 6 represents that the comprehensibility of the study can be ensured by conducting an F test where the value of F statistic is 17.512. It denotes the relationship is significant at $\alpha=0.05$ level or 5% level with 7 and 134 degrees of freedom. In this model, each of the independent variables has a different B-value, indicating that the null hypothesis can be rejected.

So, it has come to an end that consumer attitude towards clothing apparel of unique designer brands in Bangladesh can be explained by the predictors; celebrity endorsement, quality, word-of-mouth, aesthetic, personal identity, customer service, and country-of-origin.

5.5.2 Significance of Partial Coefficients

Related to the correlation results, the significance of partial coefficients can be better indicated through β (beta) coefficient values. The value of B (constant) indicates the average consumer attitude if there is no motivating attributes of a fashion clothing brand. More specifically, the β -values represent that celebrity endorsement (X1) affects consumer attitude ($P=.000$) followed by quality (X2) attribute ($P=.000$) and aesthetic aspect (X4) ($P=.001$). However, the effect of word-of-mouth ($P=.719$); customer service ($P=.276$); personal identity ($P=.828$), and country-of-origin ($P=.995$) are found insignificant in the fashion industry. Therefore, it can be stated that celebrity endorsement, quality, and aesthetic aspect are positively and significantly associated with consumer attitude formation in the fashion industry whereas the predictive ability of the rest four variables are founded insignificant in this industry. Thus, the hypotheses H1, H2, and H4 have been retained. Conversely, H3, H5, H6, and H7 are rejected as they have no significant effect on consumer attitude development. The overall adjusted R square (0.450) of the model states about 45 percent variance in the dependent variable can be interpreted by the seven predictors.

Table 7 : Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Impact
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.091	1.040		1.049	.296	
	Celebrity endorsement (X1)	.158	.032	.333	4.941	.000	Significant
	Quality (X2)	.275	.068	.308	4.070	.000	Significant
	Word-of-mouth(X3)	.028	.077	.028	.360	.719	Insignificant
	Aesthetic (X4)	.277	.081	.249	3.440	.001	Significant
	Customer Service (X5)	.071	.065	.077	1.094	.276	Insignificant
	Personal Identity (X6)	.011	.052	.015	.218	.828	Insignificant
	Country-of-origin (X7)	.001	.086	.000	.007	.995	Insignificant

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer attitude towards clothing apparel of unique designer brands in Bangladesh.

Source: SPSS output

The analytical model for Multiple Regression Analysis is given below:

$$Y^{\wedge} = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + \dots + b_kX_k$$

Here,

Y = Consumer Attitude

X₁ = Determinants of consumer attitude

a = Intercept

b_i = Slope of the line.

So, the estimated regression equation is:

$$Y^{\wedge} = 1.091 + .333X1 + .308X2 + .249X4$$

OR,

Consumer Attitude towards Clothing Apparel of Unique Designer Brands in Bangladesh (Y[^]) = 1.091+333 (Celebrity endorsement) +.308 (Quality) + .249 (Aesthetic).

6. DISCUSSION

This study empirically validates the relationship between different motivating factors or determinants of designer clothing brand purchase and consumer attitude in the context of the Bangladesh fashion industry. Previous empirical researches on clothing apparel almost ignored the “attitude” perspective of consumers and were primarily conducted on buying behavior (Chowdhury and Akter, 2018); service quality,

satisfaction, and loyalty analysis (Islam et al., 2012); purchase behavior toward local vs. foreign brand (Kumar et al., 2009); online purchase behavior (Rahman and Mannan, 2018); purchase intention (Lee et al., 2008); clothing benefits sought (Park and Sullivan, 2009); consumer decision-making style (Wang et al., 2004), clothing brand loyalty (Oh and Fiorito, 2002) and so on. The investigation of what influences “consumer attitude” with regard to designer clothing brand is found as an under-researched area in this study.

This research aims to explore how the attitudes of consumers towards fashion clothing brands can be influenced through various determinants or factors in the context of Bangladesh. This study contributes to the Consumer Behavior (CB) discipline by identifying factors that lead a consumer to shape his positive or negative attitude towards a particular clothing brand. The results indicate that three out of seven factors namely celebrity endorsement, quality, and aesthetic aspect are significantly associated with consumer attitudes. This is conforming to the earlier studies postulating that a particular celebrity can lead a consumer in drawing attention and brand recall (Jansson and Power, 2010); a quality dimension is an integral component for generating trust (North et al., 2003; Hourigan and Bougoure, 2012); an aesthetic perspective of a clothing brand can tie up a consumer emotionally (Prendergast and Wong, 2003). The results are less clear with respect to the influence of word-of-mouth, customer service, personal identity, and country-of-origin, as these components are revealed to have an insignificant relationship with “consumer attitude”. The fact that word-of-mouth was not found to have a significant implication in this sample, means that consumers are less reliant on the personal form of communication in developing clothing purchase behavior. This finding is inconsistent with the prior studies discussed in the literature review (Kiecker and Cowles, 2002; McKinney et al., 2004). With respect to customer service, the absence of a significant relationship with consumer attitude is inconsistent with the study of Moye (2000) which implies that consumers are less concerned about the customer-oriented service facilities during shopping and more focused on the main product clothing. Additionally, the finding with regard to personal identity represents an insignificant relationship with consumer attitude which is not in line with the study of Kamineni and O’Cass, (2000). It suggests that upper and upper-middle-class consumers are oriented towards utilitarian consumption as opposed to the hedonic one. Further, the source of production factor or country-of-origin element is perceived to have an insignificant association with consumer attitude formation which is not supported by the studies of (Dutton, 2006; Park et al., 2009; Jegethesan et al., 2012; Prasad, 2012). Consumers are ready to buy any branded cloth as long as the brand has quality aspects, favorable celebrity endorsement, and emotional and aesthetical attachment.

7. IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

7.1 Theoretical Implications

Academic researchers on fashion marketing have offered small-scale attention to obtain knowledge about consumer attitudes towards purchasing fashionable brands.

Specifically, hardly any research has been undertaken on identifying what influences a consumer in forming a positive or negative attitude towards designer clothing brands. Although there seems to have evidence that attitude is often undertaken as a behavioral indicator in psychology studies, contributions that offer empirical evidence regarding this were absent. The current study endeavors to address this under-researched area by considering a set of product and brand-related attributes. Clothing brands marketers are continuously trying to uncover what motivates a consumer to select a brand over another among vastly available alternatives and thus the study has contributed to the Consumer Behavior (CB) discipline by providing a depth insight into the “consumer attitude”. Theoretically, the outcomes of the study are notable as they refer to the significance of forming a positive attitude that ultimately has a carryover effect on buying behavior formation (Ajzen, 2020).

7.2 Managerial Implications

The results indicate that among the seven underlying factors or determinants identified from the literature, celebrity endorsement, quality, and aesthetic aspects have a significant relationship with customer attitude formation. However, word-of-mouth, customer service, personal identity, and country-of-origin are found insignificant for the study. Among all the identified factors, celebrity endorsement is considered as the most significant driver ($\beta = .158$) while the country-of-origin factor has the least importance in the study ($\beta = .001$). The fact that country-of-origin has a minimal significance in this study is harmonious with the work of (Kumar et al., 2009). The finding of celebrity endorsement explored as a significant driver, is uniform with the research work of Jansson and Power (2010) who found that celebrities do have a practical impact on attitude formation.

The “word-of-mouth” is measured by brand promise, family & friend’s words and spreading good words by the customers themselves. The insignificant association between WOM and consumer attitude reveals that unless and until customers experience the brands by themselves, they will not advocate that to others. The “Personal identity” factor has been measured by matching clothing color with skin, personality though unique cloth, social status and consideration of own personality. The finding regarding this factor again indicates the utilitarian-consumption-oriented character of consumers. “Customer service” factor has been measured by smooth payment facilities, knowledgeable sales staff, and shop assistance. An energetic, passionate salesperson is an asset for a company as they are considered brand representatives. Their caring attitude facilitates customers in shopping activities which will ultimately provide multiplier effects for the brand. Also, the transaction can be made easy through developing smooth payment facilities like cash payment, bKash, Rocket services, credit card punching options, etc. For example- a fashion and lifestyle brand Aarong has adopted a flexible billing and payment method where they offer a good number of payment options for the customer to choose from. A customer can make cash payments for shopping or use bKash facility for that. In the case of online ordering, they have adopted separate payment options for Bangladesh

and outside the country. In Bangladesh, anyone can use a Visa, MasterCard, Amex debit/credit/pre-paid cards, mobile wallets, and cash-on-delivery. Anyone requesting delivery to the USA can make payment via Visa, MasterCard debit/credit/ pre-paid cards only, and bKash as mobile money wallet¹. Offering multiple payment options entices customers not to leave their shopping carts at the last moment of shopping. Manufacturing country and local vs. foreign brands are used to measure the “country-of-origin” construct. Analyses have found that customers prefer shopping from local designer brands to foreign ones. The homegrown brands are making up the ground for customers that are outperforming different established foreign brands in Bangladesh. As local brands can offer reasonable prices along with a better understanding of customer tastes, a throng of the customer can be found at the outlets of local brands such as Deshi Dosh, Aarong, Anjan, Sadakalo and so forth².

The “Celebrity Endorsement” factor has been measured by four observed variables- “usage of a favorite celebrity, promotion through celebrity, the personality of celebrity and unusual style presented through celebrity”. Promotion of Aarong men and women’s wear is done through recruiting the country’s top models². Brand promotion through celebrity can be used extensively in developing a short documentary or video of 2/3 minutes on social media. During different cultural and national occasions, Kaykraft, Aarong, Le Reve use celebrities to promote their clothing apparels. These short documentaries not only touch customers from their heart but also drive them to stores and websites for further ordering of the products. Reliability, durability, perceived quality, and price-quality relationship have been selected to measure the construct “quality”, as determined by Garvin (1984). The finding of the “quality” construct states that designer clothing brands should offer clothing wearing that customers can use for an expected period. Mismatch between price and quality not only discourages customers from patronage but also leads them to spread negative word-of-mouth. For example- the unethical price charge in one branch of Aarong during Eid-ul-Adha, 2019 immediately created a huge negative perception among customers that the loyal customers stopped purchasing from them. Finally, the aesthetic factor includes fashionable design, comfort, and style altogether. Brands should produce clothing apparel that not only depicts fashion and style but also offer comfort. This is what most consumers seek from brands.

8. LIMITATIONS, CONCLUSIONS, AND DIRECTION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

As with many researches, this study has been undertaken in the midst of certain limitations. First of all, a quota sampling technique of non-probability in type has been employed. Due to the selection of quota elements on the basis of convenience or judgment, different types of selection bias are potentially present there. Secondly, some of the designer clothing brands have been selected from only two major cities- Dhaka and Chittagong. Thirdly, a small sample size of 140 respondents has been selected based on specific social classes (upper and upper-middle-class) of some particular

1. Aarong, 2021

2. The Daily Star, 2020

locations. A larger sample size, including people from other regions of the country, should be undertaken for broadening and generalizing the study. Fourthly, only a single cross-sectional research design has been adopted which gives only one-time consumer responses. Hence, a longitudinal research design is essential in the future for verifying the causal relationships among consumer attitude constructs developed in the study. Apart from this, replications in different fashion brand domains, for example, cosmetics, footwear, and personal care products and other non-fashion areas can further assist research outcomes in conceptualizing consumer attitude.

This study measures Bangladeshi consumer attitudes towards clothing apparel in the context of unique designer brands. Three out of seven underlying drivers are found to have a considerable effect on customer attitude formation. The other four elements including word-of-mouth, customer service, personal identity, and country-of-origin were found insignificant in the study. Therefore, clothing brands should focus more on these three variables and less on the rest of the four variables when designing a fine-tuning marketing strategy for attracting and retaining customers. Despite the limitations mentioned above, the current study has aimed to contribute to Consumer Behavior (CB) discipline and existing clothing literature by measuring customer attitude towards clothing apparel with regard to unique designer brands in Bangladesh.

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APPENDIX

Table A1 : General information regarding fashion clothing purchase

Variables	Yes	No	May be
Preferences for shopping	73.2	10.6	16.2
Aesthetic aspect	83.1	9.9	7.0
Customer-oriented service facilities	91.5	2.1	6.3
Attractive shopping atmosphere	62.7	16.9	20.4

	Totally unimportant (%)	Unimportant (%)	Neutral (%)	Important (%)	Very Important (%)
Pleasant shopping experience	2.8	2.1	22.5	52.8	19.7
Skilled sales person	.7	5.6	16.9	54.2	22.5
Price-quality matching	1.4	1.4	4.9	38.0	54.2
Country-specific information					
	Very low (%)	Low (%)	Medium (%)	High (%)	Very High (%)
Availability of aesthetic & atmospheric component in Bangladesh	1.4	8.5	72.5	16.2	1.4
	Very dissatisfied (%)	Dissatisfied (%)	Neutral (%)	Satisfied (%)	Very satisfied (%)
Satisfaction level with Bangladeshi fashion houses	0.7	13.4	35.2	48.6	2.1

Table A2 : Quota sampling with the control category of age and gender

Control Characteristics		Gender				Total
		Male	%	Female	%	
Age	Below 20 years	15	42.86%	20	57.14%	35
	21-30 Years	15	42.86%	20	57.14%	35
	31-40 Years	15	42.86%	20	57.14%	35
	41-50 Years	15	42.86%	20	57.14%	35
	Total	60		80		140